

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.793 Max: 63.5245	1279 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1389-95 Photo Model: Yes No #: 307

DEFINITION
layer with larger stones, pot and bones

Covered by SU: 1273 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX														
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery (f) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails (m) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles (f) <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia (m) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick (r) <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris (f) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) (m) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <u>beam weights</u> <u>LOAM?</u>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) Grey + Orange <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Travertine r <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Basalt r <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 30% silt 70% sand 0% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: 1183	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1278	Covers: 1330
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1322

OBSERVATIONS
 SU was recorded in 2010 season and excavated in the beginning of 2011 - season

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: central in Area B, east of the house and west of lead ^{immediately} sarcophagus
 Shape: long rectangular

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slight slope to the south, according to the development of the natural slope
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): no clusters
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight</p> <p>Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p> <p>see back</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1279 represents a deep fill of the bedrock cut SU 1322. It is characterized by a homogeneous, dark brown, silty soil with large tufo + limestone inclusions. Also present were large quantities of tile, dolia, ceramics (particularly black-glass), and animal bone. The rubble appears to be tumbled from the adjacent walls, while the soil was presumably washed in and around the rubble by water channelled into the N/S section of cut 1322 from the E/W section to the north.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by T. Karr

on 24.6.2011

Revised by CHH

on 28.6.2011

PDFd by AAA, AMC

on 13-7-2011, 15/7/2011

Entered by

on

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.793 Max: 63.5245	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1279 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1389-1395 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *layers with large amounts of build. mat.*
 Covered by SU: 1273 Fills SU: 1273 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Soft <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original
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 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1273	Covers: n.a.
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
is situated on the easternmost edge of Trench B 2010

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector:
 Shape: *WAS NOT EXCAVATED IN 2010*

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:
 Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

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Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

layer with larger chunks of building material, probably situated in a corridor between two houses/blocks

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *CMH + Demaine* on *30.07.2010*

Revised by *CMH* on *30.07.2010*

PDFd by *AAA, AMC* on *13.7.2011, 15/7/2011*

Entered by _____ on _____